

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP3

NA2 – Dissemination, Communication, and Collaboration

Deliverable D3.8

D-NA2.4 European White Book on Smart Energy Systems Integration and Testing

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 61 months

Beneficiary in Charge: European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories (DERlab)

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.15745472](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15745472)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Deliverable Number:	D3.8
Deliverable Full Title:	D-NA2.4 European White Book on Smart Energy Systems Integration and Testing
Deliverable Short Title:	White Book
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-D38-WhiteBook-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories (DERlab)
Report Version:	v1.4
Contractual Date:	30/04/2025
Report Submission Date:	27/06/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	T. Strasser, M. Calin (AIT), L. Ramos (DERlab)
Co-author(s):	—
Keywords:	Future Energy Systems, Sector Coupling, Multi-Domain Systems, System of Systems, Validation, Testing, Co-Simulation, Hardware-in-the-Loop, Laboratories, Research Infrastructure, Experiences, Education, Training, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> draft, <input type="checkbox"/> final, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
25/06/2025	v1.0	T. Strasser (AIT)	First document structure
26/06/2025	v1.1	T. Strasser, M. Calin (AIT), L. Ramos (DERlab)	Section inputs and final draft for review
27/06/2025	v1.2	G. Meshi (DERlab), E. Rikos (CRES)	Internal review
27/06/2025	v1.3	E. Mrakotsky (AIT)	Language and grammar review
27/06/2025	v1.4	T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	7
1.2 Structure of the Document	7
2. White Book Content.....	8
2.1 Target Audience and Use Cases	9
2.2 Development Process and Contributors	9
2.3 Structure of the Book	9
3. Conclusions	12
References	13

List of Figures

Figure 1: Cover of the upcoming ERIGrid 2.0 book (Strasser, Calin, & Ramos Perez, 2025). 8

List of Abbreviations

CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DoE	Design of Experiments
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTD	Holistic Test Description
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
OA	Open Access
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
RI	Research Infrastructure
RlasC	Research Infrastructure as Code
RTI	Research and Technology Infrastructure
TA	Transnational Access
USAT	Uncertainty Structure Analysis Tool
uAPI	universal Application Programming Interface
VSI	Virtual Shifting Impedance

Executive Summary

ERIGrid 2.0 has made substantial progress in advancing the integration, validation, and testing of smart grid and energy system solutions throughout Europe. By developing a comprehensive framework that combines holistic testing methodologies, enhanced simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop techniques, and the integration of multi-domain Research Infrastructures, the project addressed the increasing complexity of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems. These systems, which tightly link the electrical, thermal and information domains, require innovative validation approaches to ensure reliability, interoperability, and scalability.

This white book consolidates the key findings, tools, and methodologies developed throughout the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It presents a strategic vision for future research, education, and (pre-)standardisation in the domains of smart grids and energy systems validation. The content will be formally published as an Open Access volume in the SpringerBriefs in Energy series, ensuring broad dissemination and long-term accessibility. Until then, this deliverable serves as a timely and valuable resource for stakeholders seeking access to project outcomes and information. It also outlines the structure and scope of the forthcoming Open Access book.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The transition toward a decarbonised, digitalised, and decentralised energy system introduces unprecedented complexity in the design, operation, and validation of modern energy infrastructures. Smart energy systems must integrate multiple energy carriers — such as electricity and heat, alongside advanced control, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) technologies, and diverse Distributed Energy Resources (DERs). Traditional validation approaches are often focussing on isolated components, which is no longer sufficient to capture the dynamic, multi-domain interactions that characterise Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPESs).

To address these challenges, the ERIGrid 2.0 project built upon the foundation established by its predecessor, ERIGrid, by developing a pan-European network of Research and Technology Infrastructures (RTIs) and a comprehensive suite of methodologies for holistic, system-level validation. These include the Holistic Test Description (HTD) framework, advanced co-simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) techniques, harmonised benchmarks, and tools for uncertainty quantification and reproducibility. In parallel, ERIGrid 2.0 put a strong emphasis on education, (pre-)standardisation, and policy alignment to ensure long-term impact and broad adoption of its results.

This deliverable provides an executive summary and outlines the structure and content of the forthcoming Open Access (OA) book, to be published in the SpringerBriefs in Energy series. The book consolidates the key findings, tools, and methodologies developed throughout the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It articulates a strategic vision for future research, education, and (pre-)standardisation in the field of smart grid and energy systems validation. While the formal publication will be published after the project ends, this deliverable serves as a timely and valuable resource for stakeholders looking for the project outcomes and insights.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is structured as follows: Section 1 introduces the motivation and objectives. Section 2 outlines the structure and key topics of the forthcoming book. Finally, Section 3 presents the main conclusions and closing remarks.

2 White Book Content

This section provides an overview of the structure and content of the forthcoming OA book, titled “*European Guide to Smart Energy System Testing: The ERIGrid 2.0 Approach for Evaluating Complex Smart Energy System Configurations*” (Strasser et al., 2025). The book consolidates the key outcomes of the ERIGrid 2.0 project and is published as part of the SpringerBriefs in Energy series. It is intended as a comprehensive reference for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers engaged in the validation of smart energy systems.

The book captures methodological advancements, technical innovations, and strategic insights developed throughout the project, and outlines a vision for future developments in the field. It is already announced on the Springer Nature website¹, where it will be made openly accessible upon publication. The cover of the book is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cover of the upcoming ERIGrid 2.0 book (Strasser et al., 2025).

¹<https://link.springer.com/book/9783031994500>

2.1 Target Audience and Use Cases

The *European Guide to Smart Energy System Testing* is designed to serve a broad spectrum of stakeholders involved in the development, validation, and deployment of smart grids and energy systems. The primary target audience includes:

- *Researchers and Academics*: To support methodological advancements and provide a foundation for further scientific exploration in the field of CPES.
- *Engineers and Practitioners*: To offer practical tools, workflows, and case studies that can be directly applied in laboratory and field validation activities.
- *Policymakers and Regulators*: To inform policy development and (pre-)standardisation efforts by highlighting best practices and validation frameworks.
- *Educators and Trainers*: To facilitate the integration of cutting-edge validation techniques into academic curricula and professional training programmes.

The book is also intended to support use cases such as the design of cross-laboratory/infrastructure experiments, the development of interoperable control systems, and the implementation of reproducible testing procedures across distributed facilities.

2.2 Development Process and Contributors

The content of the book is the result of a collaborative effort among experts from the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium, encompassing a wide range of disciplines and institutions. The development process followed a structured editorial workflow, including:

- *Collaborative Authoring*: Each chapter was authored by domain specialists, ensuring technical depth and relevance.
- *Internal Review and Feedback*: Drafts underwent multiple rounds of internal review within the consortium to ensure consistency, clarity, and quality.
- *Integration of Project Results*: The book consolidates validated outcomes from research activities, demonstration projects, and stakeholder feedback collected during the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

This collaborative approach ensures that the book reflects both theoretical advancements and practical insights, making it a valuable reference for the broader smart energy systems community.

2.3 Structure of the Book

The book is organised into eleven chapters, each addressing a specific aspect of smart grids and energy system validation. The structure reflects the interdisciplinary and multi-domain nature of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, progressing from foundational concepts and methodologies to advanced simulation techniques, infrastructure integration, and strategic enablers such as education and (pre-)standardisation. Domain experts from the project consortium authored each chapter and included both theoretical foundations and practical applications, supported by case studies and demonstration results.

The following chapter summaries highlight the main contributions and focus areas of each part of the book:

Chapter 1: Towards Energy System Validation

Authors: T.I. Strasser, M. Calin, L.E. Ramos Perez

Introduces the motivation for holistic validation of CPESs, highlighting the increasing complexity of multi-energy systems and the critical role of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in enabling system-level testing and innovation. It outlines the ERIGrid 2.0 approach and its relevance in the context of the energy transition.

Chapter 2: Holistic Smart Energy System Validation

Authors: F. Pröbstl Andren, E. Widl, K. Heussen, E. Rikos, T.I. Strasser, P. Raussi

Presents the HTD methodology and its extensions, including structured templates for system configuration, control function modelling, and uncertainty representation. It also introduces test case profiling and the development of machine-readable test case repositories to support reproducibility and knowledge sharing.

Chapter 3: Enhanced Validation Methods and Benchmark

Authors: J. Kamsamrong, E. Widl, J.S. Schwarz, K. Heussen, P. Raussi, G. Arnold, A. De Paola, Z. Feng, O. Werth, M.C. Pham, Q.T. Tran

Describes benchmark models for electrical, multi-energy, and ICT-enhanced systems. It introduces tools for uncertainty quantification, reproducibility, and the Design of Experiments (DoE) toolbox, supporting systematic and scalable validation workflows.

Chapter 4: Extended Co-Simulation Approaches

Authors: J.S. Schwarz, E. Widl, O. Gehrke, K. Heussen, R. Fabian, J. Kamsamrong

Explores advanced co-simulation techniques for CPESs, including mosaik-based setups, Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) 3.0 integration, and real-time simulation enhancements. It addresses initialisation challenges, synchronisation issues, and multi-domain coupling strategies.

Chapter 5: Improved Hardware-in-the-Loop-based Testing

Authors: Z. Feng, M. Syed, A. Paspatis, A. Kontou, G. Lauss, A. De Paola, P. Kotsamopoulos, N. Hatziaargyriou, G. Burt

Details improvements in Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) testing, including stability and accuracy enhancements using Virtual Shifting Impedance (VSI) and adaptive Smith Predictor techniques. A novel sensitivity analysis framework is also introduced to assess the robustness of PHIL setups.

Chapter 6: Laboratory Infrastructure Integration and Automation

Authors: A. Acosta, G. Silano, G. Paludetto, O. Gehrke, M.C. Pham, Q.T. Tran, V. Rajkumar, S. Vogel, A. Monti

Discusses tools and methodologies for integrating and automating distributed RIs, including the universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI), configuration management tools, and the

Research Infrastructure as Code (RIasC) middleware. These tools enable scalable, automated, and reproducible multi-lab experiments.

Chapter 7: Sector Coupling and Multi-Domain Systems Validation

Authors: E. Widl, G. Silano, O. Gehrke, T. Zerihun

Demonstrates the validation of power-to-heat and hybrid energy systems using co-simulation and geographically distributed testing. It highlights the role of sector coupling in enhancing system flexibility, resilience, and cross-domain coordination.

Chapter 8: Experiences with Smart System Integration and Validation

Authors: G. Silano, A. Kontou, Z. Feng, A. Acosta, O. Gehrke, T. Zerihun, S. Sanchez-Acevedo, G. Arnold, J.E. Rodriguez-Seco, R. Lazzari, C. Rodio, L. Pellegrino

Summarises feedback from Transnational Access (TA) users and Key Performance Indicator (KPI) assessments. It presents lessons learned from demonstration activities and showcases the practical applicability of ERIGrid 2.0 tools and methods in real-world validation scenarios.

Chapter 9: Education Needs, Methods and Tools

Authors: A. Kontou, P. Kotsampopoulos, K. Heussen, L.E. Ramos Perez, T.I. Strasser, E. Rikos, G. Makrides, Z. Feng, P. Karafotis, A. Paspatis, M. Syed, G. Lauss, M. Calin, N. Hatziargyriou

Covers interdisciplinary training approaches, including Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), virtual and remote laboratories, and real-time simulation-based modules. It also introduces a methodology for managing educational programmes in research projects and highlights the importance of workforce development.

Chapter 10: Standardisation, Policies and Interoperability

Authors: M. Calin, G. Lauss, L.E. Ramos Perez, T.I. Strasser

Reviews the role of standardisation in CPES validation, with a focus on Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Std 2004-2025. It discusses policy frameworks, international collaboration, and the importance of interoperability for scalable, secure, and future-proof energy systems.

Chapter 11: Summary and Future Directions

Authors: T.I. Strasser, M. Calin, L.E. Ramos Perez

Concludes the book by synthesising key findings and outlining future directions. Topics include scaling multi-RI experiments, digital twin validation, advanced PHIL techniques, and the continued development of educational and standardisation frameworks.

3 Conclusions

ERIGrid 2.0 established a comprehensive, scalable, and reproducible framework for the validation of smart grids and smart energy systems, addressing the increasing complexity of CPES. The project contributions include holistic testing methodologies, advanced co-simulation and HIL techniques, multi-domain RTI integration, and efforts in education and (pre-)standardisation.

This white book consolidates the project's key outcomes across eleven chapters, each focusing on a critical aspect of smart energy system validation:

- The HTD methodology (Chapter 2) was extended to support detailed system configuration, control function modelling, and uncertainty representation, enabling structured, transparent, and reproducible test case development.
- Enhanced validation methods (Chapter 3) introduced benchmark models for electrical, multi-energy, and ICT-enhanced systems, along with tools for uncertainty quantification and reproducibility, including the Uncertainty Structure Analysis Tool (USAT) and a DoE toolbox.
- Co-simulation and real-time simulation techniques (Chapters 4 and 5) were significantly improved to support multi-domain integration. Notable advancements include FMI 3.0-based communication modelling, mosaik-based co-simulation, and advanced PHIL stability and accuracy enhancements using VSI and adaptive Smith Predictor techniques.
- Laboratory integration and automation (Chapter 6) were advanced through the development of the uAPI, configuration management tools, and the RlasC middleware, enabling scalable, automated, and cloud-enabled multi-RI experiments.
- Sector coupling and multi-energy validation (Chapter 7) demonstrated the feasibility of co-simulation and geographically distributed testing for power-to-heat and hybrid energy systems, using both virtual and physical infrastructures.
- Demonstration activities and user feedback (Chapter 8) validated the practical applicability of ERIGrid 2.0 tools and methods. Key achievements include improved PHIL fidelity, machine learning-based Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS) delay compensation, and accelerated experiment setup through harmonised configuration workflows.
- Education and training (Chapter 9) were addressed through the development of interdisciplinary MOOCs, virtual and remote labs, real-time simulation-based modules, and a structured educational programme management methodology tailored to research projects.
- Standardisation and interoperability (Chapter 10) were advanced through alignment with international frameworks, notably IEEE Std 2004-2025², significantly supported by ERIGrid 2.0, and through active contributions to the development of best practices for HIL-based testing and CPES validation.

The white book is published as an OA volume in the SpringerBriefs in Energy series.

²<https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2004/11300/>

References

Strasser, T. I., Calin, M., & Ramos Perez, L. E. (2025). *European Guide to Smart Energy System Testing: The ERIGrid 2.0 Approach for Evaluating Complex Smart Energy System Configurations*. Springer Nature. doi:[10.1007/978-3-031-99451-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-99451-7)

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2025 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

